

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

Aprillita Dian Wanodya¹, Ida Aju Brahmasari², Ida Aju Brahma Ratih³

^{1,2,3}Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

ABSTRACT: The current era of globalization is a big challenge faced by local governments. Government agencies are expected to be able to display professional apparatus, have a high work ethic, competitive advantage and have the ability to uphold bureaucratic ethics in carrying out their duties and functions in order to fulfill the aspirations of the community, namely providing the best, fast and precise service. This research aims to determine empirical evidence regarding the influence of education level, work experience and competency on career development, job satisfaction and employee performance. The population in this research were employees of the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency. The sampling technique was a saturated sample, namely all employees who worked at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency, namely 129 employees. Hypothesis testing was carried out using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). Of the 12 hypotheses analyzed, 10 hypotheses were proven to be accepted and the other 2 hypotheses were rejected.

KEYWORDS: Level of education, work experience, competency, career development, job satisfaction, employee performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The current era of globalization is a big challenge faced by local governments. Government agencies are expected to be able to display professional apparatus, have a high work ethic, competitive advantage and have the ability to uphold bureaucratic ethics in carrying out their duties and functions in order to fulfill the aspirations of the community, namely providing the best, fast and precise service. So it will be seen how high the performance of employees in that agency is.

Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning regional government, public services have become widely discussed, because public services are one of the indicators that measure the success of implementing regional autonomy. The provision of public services by government officials to the community is actually an implication of the function of state officials as public servants. Therefore, the position of government officials in public services is very strategic because it will determine the extent to which the government is able to provide the best possible service to the community. The services provided by the regional government through the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency are currently considered capable of serving the needs of the community, through extinguishing or other rescue actions.

The large number of fire cases in Bojonegoro Regency is caused by the development and increase in population, so that the risk of fires also increases. In the blackout process, of course there are several things that can hinder the blackout activities, including the limited distribution of fire stations in Bojonegoro Regency. The total area of Bojonegoro Regency is 2,307.06 Km² and is inhabited by 1,249,578 residents spread across 27 sub-districts. The wide coverage area and large population of more than one million people mean that the firefighting unit's services are less than optimal. So it is necessary to increase the distribution of fire posts so that they can meet the international standard for response time, namely 15 minutes to the crime scene.

Efforts to improve employee performance include paying attention to education level. In carrying out work, employees are also inseparable from their level of education. A bachelor's degree is a basic requirement for many jobs. However, currently, not all Fire Department employees in Bojonegoro Regency have Bachelor's level (Strata 1) education, especially employees or personnel who work in the field. This is because personnel who are in the field when working require more skills and abilities obtained from routine training conducted by the District Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro.

Organizations seek employees whose previous work experience matches the organization's current needs in the hope that such experience will help them produce more quickly (Rynes et al., 1997). The more experience a person has, the easier the skills to complete work will be. Work experience is needed to support the competencies possessed by each employee.

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

Competencies can deepen and expand a person's work abilities. The more often someone does the same job, the more skilled they are and the faster they complete the job. Employees tend to perform well if they have a clear career development path. They need to know that there are opportunities for organizational growth and advancement and feel satisfied with their journey in the world of work.

Job satisfaction is often shown by employees by liking the work itself and the level of enjoyment they have in carrying out their work. In general, it can be stated that job satisfaction is a feeling of comfort and positive relationships between fellow employees (Bakotic, 2013: 52). Job satisfaction can influence performance because job satisfaction plays an important role in company development to increase employee efficiency and performance (Ahmed, 2012:45).

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Level of Education

Level of Education according to Lestari in Wirawan (2019) "is a person's activity in developing their abilities, attitudes and forms of behavior, both for future life through certain organizations or unorganized".

The following are several indicators to measure level of education :

1. Formal education
2. Informal education

B. Work Experience

According to Foster (2015:40) work experience is a measure of the length of time or period of work that a person has taken to understand the tasks of a job and have carried them out well.

The following are several indicators to measure work experience:

1. Length of time/work period.
2. Level of knowledge and skills possessed.
3. Mastery of work and equipment.

C. Competency

Which means skill, ability and authority (Renyut, 2017).

The following are several indicators to measure competency:

1. Knowledge
2. Expertise
3. Mastery
4. Professionalism
5. Experience

D. Career Development

According to Dessler (2020:313) is defined as a series of lifelong activities that contribute to the exploration, formation, success and fulfillment of one's goals.

The following are several indicators to measure career development:

1. Have an individual development plan
2. Have access to training
3. Receive performance feedback from supervisors

E. Job Satisfaction

Robbins and Judge (2017) define job satisfaction as positive feelings about work resulting from evaluating its characteristics.

The following are several indicators to measure job satisfaction:

1. The work itself

Work provides employees with the opportunity to learn according to their interests and the opportunity to be responsible.

2. Salary

Employee job satisfaction will be formed if the amount of money the employee receives is in accordance with the workload and is balanced with other employees.

3. Promotion

Promotion is a form of appreciation received by employees in the organization. Employee job satisfaction will be high if employees are promoted based on the employee's work performance.

4. Supervision from superiors

This is shown by superiors in the form of paying attention to how well the work is done by employees, advising and helping employees as well as good communication in supervision

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

5. Coworkers

If in an organization there is a relationship between employees that is harmonious, friendly, and helps each other, it will create a conducive work group atmosphere, which will create employee job satisfaction.

F. Employee Performance

Robbin (2016:260) defines performance as a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job.

The following are several indicators to measure employee performance:

1. Quality of Work
2. Quantity
3. Timeliness
4. Effectiveness
5. Independence.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure. 1 Conceptual Framework

Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

H1: Level of education has a significant influence on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H2: Level of education has a significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H3: Level of education has a significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H4: Work experience has a significant influence on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H5: Work experience has a significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H6: Work experience has a significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H7: Competency has a significant influence on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H8: Competency has a significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H9: Competency has a significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H10: Career development has a significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H11: Career development has a significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

H12: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency.

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

This type of research is causal explanatory research which explains the causal relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables which are used to predict the general pattern of a situation. This research used secondary data which were retrieved November 2023.

B. Population

The population in this study were employees of the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency. The number of employees working at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency who were respondents in this research was 129.

C. Data Collection

The data collection technique used was a questionnaire distributed to respondents using Google Form.

D. Data Analysis Method

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using an approach Structural Equation Model (SEM) based Partial Least Square (PLS). Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether there is an effect of research variables on the others. This testing is done by analyzing the Regression Weight, i.e. Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values. The required limits are ≥ 1.96 for the CR value and ≤ 0.05 for the P-value. If the data processing results show a value that meets these requirements, the proposed research hypothesis is accepted.

V. RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

Figure. 2 Measurement Model

Chi-Square probability value is greater than 0.05, RMSEA is less than 0.08, GFI and AGFI are greater than 0.90, Cmin/DF is less than 2.00, TLI is more than 0.90 and CFI is more than 0, 90. These results indicate that the independent variables (exogenous) level of education, work experience, competence and commitment variables (endogenous) performance, career development and job satisfaction formed by the indicators are in accordance (fit) with the data.

B. Evaluation of Structural Model/ Inner Model

After the assumptions underlying the SEM analysis have been fulfilled, a model suitability test is then carried out to ensure that the model fits the data, so that later the model can be used for hypothesis testing. The following are the results of calculating the values of the goodness of fit indices produced by the structural model:

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

Table. 1 Overall Model Goodness of Fit Value

Fit Measure		Critical Value	Structural model	
			Index value	Decision
Absolute Fit Indices	Prob. χ^2	> 0,05	0,074	Good fit
	Cmin/DF	\leq 3,00	1,144	Good fit
	GFI	\geq 0,90	0,868	Marginal fit
	RMSEA	\leq 0,08	0,034	Good fit
	SRMR	\leq 0,08	0,054	Good fit
Incremental Fit Indices	CFI	\geq 0,95	0,978	Good fit
	TLI	\geq 0,95	0,974	Good fit
	NFI	\geq 0,90	0,853	Marginal fit
	RFI	\geq 0,90	0,822	Marginal fit
Parsimony Fit Indices	AGFI	\geq 0,90	0,927	Marginal fit

the results of the structural model suitability test show that all the criteria for absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices have met the requirements (good fit and marginal fit). Thus the structural model can be accepted. Good fit means the model developed in this research provides a good fit to the empirical data, while marginal fit means the model fit is within acceptable limits.

Table. 2 Hypothesis Test Results

Direct Influence	Std. Estimate	C.R.	P-value	Hypothetical Decisions
Level of education(X1) → Career development (Z1)	0,280	2,647	0,008	H ₁ Accepted
Level of education (X1) → Job satisfaction (Z2)	0,148	1,346	0,178	H ₂ Rejected
Level of education (X1) → Employee performance (Y)	0,086	1,015	0,310	H ₃ Rejected
Work experience (X2) → Career development (Z1)	0,283	2,795	0,005	H ₄ Accepted
Work experience (X2) → Job satisfaction (Z2)	0,289	2,752	0,006	H ₅ Accepted
Work experience (X2) → Employee performance (Y)	0,228	2,393	0,017	H ₆ Accepted
Competency (X3) → Career development (Z1)	0,386	3,705	0,000	H ₇ Accepted
Competency (X3) → Job satisfaction (Z2)	0,361	3,098	0,002	H ₈ Accepted
Competency (X3) → Employee performance (Y)	0,321	2,801	0,005	H ₉ Accepted
Career development (Z1) → Job satisfaction (Z2)	0,286	2,116	0,034	H ₁₀ Accepted
Career development (Z1) → Employee performance (Y)	0,250	2,071	0,038	H ₁₁ Accepted
Job satisfaction (Z2) → Employee performance (Y)	0,325	2,023	0,043	H ₁₂ Accepted

Based on the analysis of the influence between variables, each hypothesis can be explained as follows :

1. The Influence of Education Level on Employee Career Development at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the level of education has a positive and significant effect on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.280. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 2.647 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.008 which meets the testing requirements <0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that the level of education influences career development in this research can be accepted as true.

2. The Influence of Education Level on Employee Job Satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the level of education has a positive but not significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between these two variables was obtained at 0.148. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 1.346 which does not meet the requirements >1.96 with a probability = 0.178 which meets the testing requirements <0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that the level of education influences job satisfaction in this study is rejected or cannot be accepted as true.

3. The Influence of Education Level on Employee Performance at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the level of education has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between these two variables was obtained at 0.086. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 1.015 which does not meet the requirements > 1.96 with a probability = 0.310 which meets the testing requirements < 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that the level of education influences performance in this research is rejected or cannot be accepted as true.

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

4. The Influence of Work Experience on Employee Career Development at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that work experience has a positive and significant effect on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between these two variables was obtained at 0.283. Testing shows significant results with a CR value = 2.795 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.005 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that work experience influences career development in this research can be accepted as true.

5. The Influence of Work Experience on Employee Job Satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that work experience has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees of the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.289. Testing shows significant results with a CR value = 0.289 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.006 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that work experience influences job satisfaction in this research can be accepted as true.

6. The Influence of Work Experience on Employee Performance at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

Hypothesis testing results prove that work experience has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between these two variables was obtained at 0.228. Testing shows significant results with a CR value = 2.393 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.017 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that work experience influences performance in this research can be accepted as true.

7. The Influence of Competency on Employee Career Development at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that competency has a positive and significant effect on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.386. Testing shows significant results with a CR value = 3.705 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.000 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that competence influences career development in this research can be accepted as true.

8. The Influence of Competency on Employee Job Satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.361. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 3.098 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.002 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that competence influences job satisfaction in this research can be accepted as true.

9. The Influence of Competency on Employee Performance at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that competence has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.321. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 2.801 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.005 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that competence influences performance in this research can be accepted as true.

10. The Influence of Career Development on Employee Job Satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that career development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.286. Testing shows significant results with a CR value = 2.116 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.034 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that career development influences job satisfaction in this research can be accepted as true.

11. The Influence of Career Development on Employee Performance at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that career development has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between these two variables is 0.250. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 2.071 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability = 0.038 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that career development influences performance in this research can be accepted as true.

12. The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

The results of hypothesis testing prove that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The estimated parameter for the causal relationship between the two variables was obtained at 0.325. The test shows significant results with a CR value = 2.023 fulfilling the requirements >1.96 with probability

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

= 0.043 which meets the testing requirements <0.05 . Thus, the hypothesis which states that job satisfaction influences performance in this research can be accepted as true.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the problem formulation, literature review, analysis of research results and discussions described in the previous chapters, the results of this research can be concluded as follows:

1. Level of education has a positive and significant effect on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm the theory put forward by Lestari in Wirawan (2016: 3) which states that "a person's activity in developing their abilities, attitudes and forms of behavior, both for future life through certain organizations or unorganized" and Dessler's theory (2020:313) which states that a series of lifelong activities contribute to a person's exploration, formation, success and fulfillment of their goals. The research results are the same as research conducted by Ayuni, I Wayan Sujana, Novarini (2022) who found that level had a positive and significant influence on career development.
2. Level of education has a positive but not significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research cannot confirm the theory put forward by Lestari in Wirawan (2016: 3) which states that "a person's activity in developing their abilities, attitudes and forms of behavior, both for future life through certain organizations or unorganized" and cannot confirm the theory of Robbins and Judge (2017) which states that job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work resulting from evaluating its characteristics. The results of this research are different from research conducted by Fauzi and Ubaidillah (2022) which found that education level had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
3. Level of education has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The research results cannot confirm Lestari's theory in Wirawan (2016: 3) which states that "a person's activity in developing their abilities, attitudes and forms of behavior, both for future life through certain organizations or unorganized" and the theory cannot confirm Robbin's theory (2016: 260) which states that performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job. The results of this research are different from research conducted by Nuzleha (2021) which found that the level of education has a significant contribution and influence on employee performance.
4. Work experience has a positive and significant influence on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The research results can confirm Foster's theory (2015:40) which states that work experience is a measure of the length of time or working period that a person has taken to understand the tasks of a job and have carried it out well and career development theory according to Dessler (2020:313) which states that a lifelong set of activities that contribute to a person's exploration, formation, success, and fulfillment of goals. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Novelya and Karuehni (2023) who found that work experience has a significant effect on career development.
5. Work experience has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm Foster's theory (2015: 40) which states that work experience is a measure of the length of time or period of work that a person has completed in understanding the tasks of a job and has carried it out well and the theory of Robbins and Judge (2017) which states that job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work that results from evaluating its characteristics. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Badaruddin et al (2022) which found that work experience had a positive and statistically significant effect on performance.
6. Work experience has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm Foster's theory (2015:40) which states that work experience is a measure of the length of time or period of work that a person has completed in understanding the tasks of a job and has carried it out well and Robbin's theory (2016:260) which states that performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Yanthi et al (2023) which found that work experience has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
7. Competency has a positive and significant influence on the career development of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm the theory (Renyut, 2017) which states that "competency" which means skills, abilities and authority as well as Dessler's theory (2020:313) which states that career development is a series of lifelong activities that contribute to exploration, formation, success, and fulfillment of one's goals. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Restutanti Borman et al (2023) which found that competence has a significant effect on career development.
8. Competency has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm the theory (Renyut, 2017) which states that competence means skill, ability and authority as well as the theory of Robbins and Judge (2017) which states that job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work resulting from evaluating its characteristics. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Aprilliansyah and Chalid (2020) found that competency has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction.

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

9. Competency has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm the theory (Renyut, 2017) which states that "competency" which means skills, abilities and authority as well as Robbin's theory (2016:260) which states that performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria specified applies to a job. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Nugraha et al., (2022) which found that competence influences employee performance.

10. Career development has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction at the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm Dessler's theory (2020:313) which states that career development is a series of lifelong activities that contribute to the exploration, formation, success and fulfillment of one's goals and the theory of Robbins and Judge (2017) which states that job satisfaction is a feeling positive attitude about a job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Susilo and Wulansari (2023) who found that career development had a significant positive impact on job satisfaction.

11. Career development has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm Dessler's theory (2020:313) which states that career development is a series of lifelong activities that contribute to the exploration, formation, success and fulfillment of one's goals and Robbin's theory (2016:260) which states that performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Wiryawan and Rahmawati (2020) which found that career development had a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

12. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Fire and Rescue Service employees in Bojonegoro Regency. The results of this research can confirm the theory of Robbins and Judge (2017) which states that job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work resulting from evaluating its characteristics and the theory of Robbin (2016: 260) which states that performance is a result achieved by employees in their work according to criteria: specific ones that apply to a job. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by S Egenius et al (2020) which found that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance.

SUGGESTION

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. The results of this research can be used as a source of ideas and input for the development of this research in the future. In further research, it could be considered to add variables that can influence career development, job satisfaction and performance other than the variables used in this research.
2. The results of this research can be used as input for officials within the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency to pay more attention to employee education levels on job satisfaction and resulting performance.

REFERENCES

- 1) Akhwanul akhmal, fitriani lala, ruri aditya sari' (2023) "Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir dan Beban Kerja terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan," *Jurnal Bisnis, Manajemen, dan Keuangan*, 3(3), hal. 906–918. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.21009/jbmk.0303.22>.
- 2) Aprilliansyah, D. P., & Chalid, I. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pegawai Dinas Perkebunan Provinsi Kalimantan Timur. *Borneo Student Research (BSR)*, 2(1), 519–528.
- 3) Ayuni, P.D.S., I Wayan Sujana dan Novarini, N.N.A. (2022) "Pengaruh Tingkat Pendidikan, Pengalaman Kerja Dan Prestasi Kerja Terhadap Pengembangan Karir Karyawan Pada Cv. Pondok Antik," *Jurnal Emas*, 3(6), hal. 202–217.
- 4) Azlina, Y. (2019) "Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pegawai Pada Pt Kimia Farma (Persero) Tbk Jakarta," *Jurnal AKRAB JUARA*, 4(November), hal. 226–238.
- 5) Beardwell, J. dan Thompson, A. (2020) *Human resource management: Apple's enterprise approach*.
- 6) Faronsyah, M.I. dan Trisninawati (2020) "Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan PT Jasa Raharja Putera Palembang," *Ilmiah Bina Manajemen*, 3(2), hal. 113–121.
- 7) Fauzi, M.A. dan Ubaidillah, H. (2022) "The Influence of Organizational Culture, Education Level, and Compensation on Employee Job Satisfaction," *Indonesian Journal of Education Methods Development*, 20, hal. 1–14. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.21070/ijemd.v20i.672>.
- 8) Ford, M.E. dan Smith, P.R. (2020) *Motivating Self and Others, Motivating Self and Others*. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108869164>.
- 9) Khaer, N. dan Hidayati, U. (2023) "Pengaruh Kompetensi, Prestasi Kerja, dan Pengalaman Kerja terhadap Pengembangan Karier Pegawai Kantor Wilayah Kementerian Agama Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan," 5(1), hal. 34–44.
- 10) Hidayat, A. et al. (2020) "Pengaruh Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Pada Dinas Sosial Kota

The Influence of Education Level, Work Experience and Competency on Career Development, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Fire and Rescue Service in Bojonegoro Regency

Makassar,” *Jurnal Mirai Managemnt*, 6(1), hal. 2597–4084.

- 11) Hitalessy, V., Roni, H. dan Iswandi, I. (2018) “Pengaruh Tingkat Pendidikan, Pelatihan Dan Pengalaman Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan,” *Image : Jurnal Riset Manajemen*, 7(1), hal. 38–44. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.17509/image.v7i1.23137>.
- 12) Krisnawati, N.K.D. dan Bagia, I.W. (2021) “Pengaruh Kompetensi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan,” *Bisma: Jurnal Manajemen*, 7(1), hal. 29. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.23887/bjm.v7i1.28736>.
- 13) Laila Ali Marpaung dan Yahya Tanjung (2023) “Pengaruh Penilaian Prestasi Kerja, Promosi Jabatan Dan Kompetensi Pegawai Terhadap Pengembangan Karir Aparatur Sipil Negara (ASN) Pada Dinas Perindustrian Kota Medan,” *JUBIMA : Jurnal Bintang Manajemen*, 1(1), hal. 251–272.
- 14) Nargis Lusia, Kamariah, & Fitriana Nina. (2018). Pengaruh Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Dan Dampaknya Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pt (Persero) Pln Di Palembang. *Jurnal Kompetitif*, 7(2), 65–77.
- 15) Nugraha, D.A. *et al.* (2022) “Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Yang Berdampak Pada Kinerja Pegawai Negeri Sipil Dinas Kelautan Dan Perikanan Provinsi Jawa Barat,” *At-Tadbir : jurnal ilmiah manajemen*, 6(1), hal. 81. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.31602/atd.v6i1.5886>.
- 16) Nuzleha, N.L. (2021) “Analisis Tingkat Pendidikan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Kependudukan Dan Pencatatan Sipil Provinsi Lampung,” *Motivasi*, 6(2), hal. 117. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.32502/mti.v6i2.3777>.
- 17) Novelya, S. dan Karuehni, I. (2023) “Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Pengalaman Kerja Terhadap Pengembangan Karir Melalui Prestasi Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening *The Effect of Competence and Work Experience on Career Development Through Work Achievement as an Intervening Variable*,” *Jurnal Manajemen Sains dan Organisasi*, 4(2), hal. 155–165.
- 18) Pancasasti, R.P. (2022) “Pengaruh Pelatihan, Kompetensi, Dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pt. Krakatau Steel Tbk,” *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 4(02), hal. 210–227. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.47080/jmb.v4i02.2177>.
- 19) SIHOTANG, A.C. (2020) “Pengaruh Pengembangan Karier Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Showroom Lestari Mobilindo,” *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Kesatuan*, 8(3), hal. 295–304. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.37641/jimkes.v8i3.393>.
- 20) Sinaga, H.H.U. dan Wahyanti, C.T. (2019) “Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir Dan Kompensasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pt Pln (Persero) Uid Jateng & D.I Yogyakarta,” *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Humaniora*, 8(2), hal. 184. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.23887/jish-undiksha.v8i2.21400>.
- 21) Susilo, S.R. dan Wulansari, P. (2023) “Pengaruh Pengembangan Karier Dan Pelatihan Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Taiho Nusantara,” *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, & Akuntansi (MEA)*, 7(2), hal. 535–551. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.31955/mea.v7i2.3043>.
- 22) Sunarsi, D. *et al.* (2020) “Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Pengembangan Karir terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT. Berkah Cemerlang di Jakarta,” *Jurnal Ilmu Komputer dan Bisnis*, 11(2), hal. 2465–2472. Tersedia pada: <https://doi.org/10.47927/jikb.v11i2.9>.
- 23) Wiryawan, K.A. dan Rahmawati, P.. (2020) “Pengaruh Tingkat Pendidikan dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada PT. Bank Pembangunan Daerah Bali Cabang Seririt,” *Jurnal Manajemen*, 6(2), hal. 86–95.
- 24) Wirawan, ketud edy, Bagia, i wayan dan Susila, gede putu agus jana (2023) “PENGARUH TINGKAT PENDIDIKAN DAN PENGALAMAN KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA KARYAWAN,” 5(1), hal. 34–44.